

ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CSR AND FIRM RISK IN EMERGING MARKETS: A QUANTITATIVE APPROACH

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

A growing interest in business sustainability from various stakeholders, including investors, employees, suppliers, customers, government, and society, has driven firms to integrate CSR into management practices, going beyond legal requirements to address stakeholder needs and create positive impacts (Benlemlih et al., 2018; Yoon et al., 2018; De Giuli et al., 2024). Consumers, employees, and investors increasingly prioritize and reward firms that actively invest in sustainable development beyond regulatory requirements while penalizing those that fail to integrate these practices into their operations (PwC, 2021; Shakil, 2021).

CSR becomes integral to sustainable development, emphasizing balanced progress in environmental, social, and governance (ESG) aspects, and is often embedded within firms' ESG strategies (Serikakhmetova & Adambekova, 2022). CSR provides a firm with a framework for sustainability initiatives and responsible practices, while ESG reflects the measurable outcomes of a firm's overall sustainability performance valued by investors (Kaźmierczak, 2022). CSR practices are self-regulated and qualitative, leading to variation and challenges in definition across firms, while ESG offers investors measurable criteria for evaluating opportunities (O'Neill, 2024). Scholars view a firm's CSR investments as a risk management strategy that offers insurance-like protection (Benlemlih et al., 2018). With the rapid global expansion of CSR in both academia and real-world practice, numerous studies have explored how CSR engagement affects firm risk (Jo & Na, 2012).

Theories such as stakeholder, legitimacy, and agency offer different perspectives on the relationship between CSR and firm risk. Stakeholder and legitimacy theories propose that CSR reduces risk by aligning business practices with societal

values and balancing stakeholder interests, leading to improving risk management, increasing transparency, and better access to financial markets (Jo & Na, 2012). Conversely, agency theory suggests that CSR may increase risk when managers overinvest in CSR for personal entrenchment, diverting resources from essential projects and weakening competitiveness (Cespa & Cestone, 2007; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2015). The emergence of the "anti-ESG" movement, which opposes integrating environmental, social, and governance criteria in investments, has led to the creation of "anti-ESG" funds and legal restrictions, pushing some firms to reassess their ESG strategies and prompting laws in various jurisdictions to restrict the use of ESG criteria in investments (ESGVoices, n.d.).

Many empirical studies investigate the impact of CSR on a firm risk, including both systematic and unsystematic risk (De Giuli et al., 2024). Theoretically, CSR can affect firm risk, both systematic and unsystematic, in either a positive or negative direction (Ayton et al., 2022). Previous studies find that CSR can have significant positive, negative, mixed, and insignificant effects on firm risk in the context of different industries and countries (Shakil, 2021). Ayton et al. (2022) indicate that while there is a general consensus in the literature that CSR is associated with reduced market risk, including total, systematic, and idiosyncratic risks, there are arguments that CSR could, in some instances, increase firm risk.

Most previous empirical studies focus on listed firms in developed markets, with less attention to non-listed firms and emerging markets, limiting a comprehensive understanding of CSR-risk relationship (De Giuli, 2024). The key differences between developed and emerging markets result from their institutional contexts, particularly in areas such as capital markets, corporate risk profiles, and environmental legitimacy (Garcia et al., 2017). In developed markets, capital systems are strong and well-regulated, but in emerging markets, oversight is weaker, and the systems are less developed. Investors in developed countries can easily access reliable information about companies, while in emerging markets, trustworthy data is harder to come by. Additionally, ESG efforts are often encouraged and even pressured in developed markets, whereas they tend to be much lower in emerging markets (Järvinen, 2022). These variations can significantly influence research outcomes across countries, as corporate social responsibility in developing regions is often shaped by local factors and governance systems (Garcia et al., 2017). The evolution of risk in emerging economies likely influences this relationship, and examining the interactions between different markets could provide valuable insights (De Giuli, 2024; Nirino et al., 2022).

There are other gaps in the CSR-firm risk relationship that require exploration in emerging markets. Chen et al. (2024) and Lee and Koh (2024) suggest that conducting industry/sector-specific analyses is essential for understanding the impact of ESG initiatives on each sector/industry. In addition, Zhao et al. (2023) and Lee

and Koh (2024) propose that future research should explore the distinct effects of individual ESG pillars on firm risk and uncover the factors driving these relationships.

Research Question

The research aims to investigate the relationship between CSR and risk in emerging markets, with a particular focus on ASEAN countries, considering overall ESG performance as well as industry-specific factors and individual ESG pillars.

The research questions are:

1. How does CSR, through the overall ESG performance and each ESG pillar performance, relate to firm risk in ASEAN countries?
2. How does CSR, through the overall ESG performance and each ESG pillar performance, influence the relationship with firm risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations?

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Study design

Type of study: This study adopts a quantitative research design to statistically analyze the relationship between CSR and firm risk.

Approach: This study employs panel data regression techniques, including OLS, fixed effects, and random effects models, to examine the relationship between ESG performance and firm risk in ASEAN countries. OLS provides a baseline for analyzing linear relationships but may introduce bias due to unobserved firm-specific characteristics. The fixed effects model addresses this by controlling for time-invariant factors, offering more precise estimates while excluding time-invariant variables. In contrast, the random effects model assumes no correlation between unobserved effects and explanatory variables, allowing for greater efficiency when the assumption holds. The Hausman test determines the appropriate model selection for reliable results. The study focuses on the impact of CSR on firm risk, considering both overall ESG performance and individual pillars (E, S, and G) to provide detailed insights into their effects.

Data Collection

Data Source: This study will utilize the Bloomberg terminal to gather ESG performance data, both aggregate and individual pillar, along with all relevant data.

Timeframe: The study will cover the period from 2021 to 2023, as ESG ratings for listed firms were less available before 2021.

Sampling Method: The study focuses on listed firms in ASEAN countries with ESG ratings as representatives of emerging markets characterized by rapid economic growth, diverse sectors, and increasing adoption of CSR practices. These markets can provide a unique perspective to the CSR-risk relationship as they transition from developing to more advanced stages. As regulatory frameworks and stakeholder expectations around sustainability continue to evolve, analyzing these markets provides valuable insights into CSR-risk dynamics that differ from those in developed economies.

Six countries mandate specific forms of ESG disclosure, with governments providing guidelines to assist publicly listed firms in preparing sustainability information (Pan, 2021). Those countries include Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. The stock exchanges of all six countries are part of the UN's Sustainable Stock Exchange (SSE) Initiative, which promotes global collaboration among exchanges, investors, firms, and regulators to improve ESG performance and support sustainable investment, including financing the UN Sustainable Development Goals (Pan, 2021; SSE, n.d.).

Data Analysis: Data analysis will be conducted entirely using STATA, covering panel data regression, diagnostic testing, and handling large datasets. STATA's strength in managing fixed and random effects models makes it ideal for this study, ensuring accurate visualization, consistency, and reproducibility of results.

Variables and Measures

Dependent variable: Firm risk

There are two categories of firm risk measurement in prior research. The first is capital market data-based measurement, and the second is accounting information-based measurement (Zhao et al., 2023). Differences in tax laws across industries and inconsistencies in accounting practices for R&D and advertising expenses can distort accounting-based measures (Amit & Wernerfelt, 1990). This study will use market-based measurement for firm risk, including total risk, systematic risk, and idiosyncratic risk. In financial studies, firm risk is divided into systematic risk, which represents the firm's sensitivity to overall market movements or changes relevant to all stocks, and idiosyncratic (unsystematic) risk, which represents the volatility of returns due to firm-specific events and cannot be explained by overall market movements (Ayton et al., 2022; Luo & Bhattacharya, 2009).

Total risk can be measured by the variance or the standard deviation of the stock returns over the period (Bouslah et al., 2013; Jo & Na, 2012; Orlitzky & Benjamin, 2001), where a higher variance or standard deviation indicates higher risk.

Systematic risk (beta) is the sensitivity of the stock price to the movement of the whole market, usually measured with the market beta (Ayton et al., 2022). Stock

beta can be calculated by dividing the covariance between stock and market returns by the variance of market returns.

Idiosyncratic risk is the residual risk that is left after accounting for the systematic risk. It can be calculated by subtracting the systematic risk from firm risk (variance of stock returns).

Independent variable

ESG performance: Aggregate ESG and individual pillar performance of each listed firm are represented by aggregate ESG score and individual pillar (E, S, and G) score from the Bloomberg terminal.

Sector-specific: Sector dummy variables based on the Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS).

Control variable

Following previous studies (Jo & Na, 2012; Shakil, 2021; Ayton, 2022; Zhao et al., 2023), the study will include the following set of variables that might explain ESG performance: financial leverage, firm size, profitability, and market-to-book value.

Table 1: Description of the Variables and Measurements

Variables	Source	Measurement
<u>Dependent variables</u>	Bloom- berg	Variance of daily stock returns
Firm risk		Market β (covariance between stock and market returns / variance of market returns)
Systematic risk		
Idiosyncratic risk		Firm risk minus systematic risk (Variance of stock returns – variance of systematic risk); where variance of systematic risk = β^2 x variance of market returns

<u>Independent variables</u> ESG performance Environmental Social Government Sector specific	Bloom-berg	Aggregate ESG score E score S score G score Healthcare = 0 Communication = 1, otherwise = 0 Consumer staples = 1, otherwise = 0 Consumer discretionary = 1, otherwise = 0 Energy = 1, otherwise = 0 Financials = 1, otherwise = 0 Industrials = 1, otherwise = 0 Materials = 1, otherwise = 0 Real estate = 1, otherwise = 0 Technology = 1, otherwise = 0 Utilities = 1, otherwise = 0
<u>Control variables</u> Leverage Firm size Profitability Market-to-book value	Bloom-berg	Total debt / total assets Natural logarithm of total assets Return on Assets (Net income / Total assets) Market price / book value of equity, measured as of the end of fiscal year

FINDINGS

The study is currently in the development stage, with the literature review highlighting previous studies that show significant positive, negative, mixed, and insignificant influences of ESG on firm risk across various industries and countries (Shakil, 2021).

Aligned with stakeholder and legitimacy theories, numerous studies consistently show that CSR activities reduce firm risk. Orlitzky and Benjamin (2001) find that CSR performance is associated with lower firm risk, with CSR investments lowering external market-based risk more than internal accounting-based risk. Several studies also indicate that CSR activities reduce systematic, idiosyncratic, and total

risks. Luo and Bhattacharya (2009) find that CSR lowers systematic and idiosyncratic risks, with moral capital providing insurance-like protection. Similarly, Salama et al. (2011), and Jo and Na (2012) demonstrate that CSR reduces systematic risk. Mishra and Modi (2013) and Kongpreecha (2021) highlight that positive CSR decreases idiosyncratic risk. Sassen et al. (2016) and Nirino et al. (2022) further confirm that CSR and ESG activities significantly reduce idiosyncratic and total risks, while systematic risk is more industry-specific. Ayton et al. (2022) and Sciarelli et al. (2023) find that CSR can reduce idiosyncratic risk, but has no significant relationship with systematic risk. Finally, Lee and Koh (2024) report that ESG performance reduces total, idiosyncratic, and systematic risks in U.S. financial firms, with strong effects from the social and governance pillars.

In contrast, research supporting agency theory suggests a different perspective. Barnea and Rubin (2010) find that overinvestment in CSR by managers and large shareholders increases overall firm risk, particularly by creating conflicts with non-affiliated shareholders. In terms of idiosyncratic risk, Becchetti et al. (2015) highlight that U.S. firms experience increased idiosyncratic risk due to CSR reducing their flexibility in responding to negative shocks, while Humphrey et al. (2012) find no difference in idiosyncratic risk between firms with high and low CSR ratings. For systematic risk, Park et al. (2017) find no significant relationship between CSR and systematic risk in U.S. restaurant firms, though geographical diversification may increase it. Chollet and Sandwidi (2018) also show that CSR engagement increases systematic risk due to investor perceptions of higher risk from information asymmetry. Lastly, Tian (2022) finds that ESG performance increases financial risk, driven by cost-ineffectiveness.

Based on the current theory and empirical evidence, the following theoretical diagram and hypotheses are proposed to address the research questions:

H1: The overall ESG score is negatively related to total risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, and the strength of this relationship varies within different sectors.

- H1a: The Environmental score is negatively related to total risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H1b: The Social score is negatively related to total risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H1c: The Governance score is negatively related to total risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H2: The overall ESG score is negatively related to systematic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, and the strength of this relationship varies within different sectors.
- H2a: The Environmental score is negatively related to systematic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H2b: The Social score is negatively related to systematic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H2c: The Governance score is negatively related to systematic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H3: The overall ESG score is negatively related to idiosyncratic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, and the strength of this relationship varies within different sectors.
- H3a: The Environmental score is negatively related to idiosyncratic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H3b: The Social score is negatively related to idiosyncratic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.
- H3c: The Governance score is negatively related to idiosyncratic risk across various sectors in ASEAN countries, with sector-specific variations.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study contributes to the existing literature on CSR-firm risk relationship by focusing on listed firms in ASEAN countries, a rapidly growing yet underexplored emerging market in CSR-risk research. Unlike previous studies that focus primarily on developed markets, this study aims to provide insights into the unique dynamics of CSR and firm risk in the ASEAN region, where the economic landscape is diverse, regulatory frameworks vary, and sustainability practices are rapidly evolving.

This study further distinguishes itself by conducting a sector-specific analysis across multiple sectors, providing a deeper understanding of how each ESG pillar—environmental, social, and governance—impacts firm risk individually. This approach allows for identifying specific risks associated with each pillar, which is crucial for developing targeted risk management strategies.

This study's findings aim to enhance academic discussions and provide practical insights for investors, regulators, and companies seeking to manage firm risk through strategic CSR and ESG initiatives. Managers can leverage CSR to manage both systematic and idiosyncratic risks, enhancing resilience against market fluctuations. For investors, incorporating ESG criteria can mitigate risks and improve long-term stability, especially in emerging markets. Policymakers in ASEAN can utilize these insights to strengthen regulations promoting corporate responsibility and transparency. Additionally, the study advocates for improved ESG reporting standards to help businesses manage risk while contributing to broader societal objectives.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

The research presented in this document highlights several limitations, which provide opportunities for further exploration:

1. **Reliance on Secondary Data:** The study's reliance on secondary data may introduce biases, suggesting that future research could benefit from primary data collection for a deeper understanding of the CSR-risk relationship.
2. **Timeframe Limitations:** The study's 2021-2023 timeframe may not capture long-term trends in ESG performance and firm risk, suggesting future research should conduct longitudinal studies beyond 2023 to observe this changing relationship more accurately.
3. **Data Sources:** The study's reliance on Bloomberg ESG ratings may limit the depth and diversity of ESG dimensions captured. Different ESG rating providers use different methodologies and criteria for evaluating firms, leading to variations in how ESG activities are assessed. Future research could explore other ESG rating providers to better understand firms' ESG activities.
4. **Exclusion of other emerging markets:** The study is limited to listed firms with ESG ratings in ASEAN countries. Future research should consider the CSR-risk relationship in other emerging markets, or explore non-listed firms to provide a broader perspective.
5. **Measurement of Firm Risk:** The study focuses on market-based risks such as total, systematic, and idiosyncratic risk, suggesting that exploring non-market risks could enhance the understanding of how ESG performance affects overall firm risk.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amit, R., & Wernerfelt, B. (1990). Why Do Firms Reduce Business Risk? In *The Academy of Management Journal* (Vol. 33, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.5465/256579>
- Ayton, J., Krasnikova, N., & Malki, I. (2022). Corporate social performance and financial risk: Further empirical evidence using higher frequency data. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, *80*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2022.102030>
- Barnea, A., & Rubin, A. (2010). Corporate Social Responsibility as a Conflict Between Shareholders. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *97*(1), 71–86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-010-0496-z>
- Becchetti, L., Ciciretti, R., & Hasan, I. (2015). Corporate social responsibility, stakeholder risk, and idiosyncratic volatility. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, *35*, 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2015.09.007>
- Benlemlih, M., Shaukat, A., Qiu, Y., & Trojanowski, G. (2018). Environmental and Social Disclosures and Firm Risk. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *152*(3), 613–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3285-5>
- Bouslah, K., Kryzanowski, L., & M'Zali, B. (2013). The impact of the dimensions of social performance on firm risk. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, *37*(4), 1258–1273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2012.12.004>
- Cespa, G., & Cestone, G. (2007). Corporate social responsibility and managerial entrenchment. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, *16*(3), 741–771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9134.2007.00156.x>
- Chen, F., Liu, Y. hu, & Chen, X. zhao. (2024). ESG performance and business risk—Empirical evidence from China's listed companies. *Innovation and Green Development*, *3*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.igd.2024.100142>
- Chollet, P., & Sandwidi, B. W. (2018). CSR engagement and financial risk: A virtuous circle? International evidence. *Global Finance Journal*, *38*, 65–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2018.03.004>
- De Giuli, M. E., Grechi, D., & Tanda, A. (2024). What do we know about ESG and risk? A systematic and bibliometric review. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, *31*(2), 1096–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2624>
- ESG Voices. (n.d.). *Anti-ESG movement: Voices challenging ESG investing*. ESG Voices. Retrieved September 12, 2024, from <https://www.esgvoices.com/post/anti-esg-movement-voices-challenging-esg-investing#viewer-w7461944497>
- Garcia, A. S., Mendes-Da-Silva, W., & Orsato, R. J. (2017). Sensitive industries produce better ESG performance: Evidence from emerging markets. *Journal of cleaner production*, *150*, 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.180>
- Humphrey, J. E., Lee, D. D., & Shen, Y. (2012). Does it cost to be sustainable? *Journal of Corporate Finance*, *18*(3), 626–639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2012.03.002>
- Järvinen, J. (2022). ESG performance in emerging markets: Evidence from the BRICS countries. <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2022031523670>
- Jo, H., & Na, H. (2012). Does CSR Reduce Firm Risk? Evidence from Controversial Industry Sectors. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *110*(4), 441–456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1492-2>

- Kaźmierczak, M. (2022). A literature review on the difference between CSR and ESG. *Scientific Papers of Silesian University of Technology. Organization and Management Series*, 2022(162), 275–289. <https://doi.org/10.29119/1641-3466.2022.162.16>
- Kongpreecha, N. (2021). The impact of ESG performance on firm-idiosyncratic risk in the US and Canada. <https://digital.car.chula.ac.th/chulaetd>
- Lee, J., & Koh, K. (2024). ESG performance and firm risk in the U.S. financial firms. *Review of Financial Economics*, 42(3), 328–344. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rfe.1208>
- Luo, X., Bhattacharya, C. B. (2009). The debate over doing good: Corporate social performance, strategic marketing levers, and firm-idiosyncratic risk. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(6), 198–213. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.73.6.198>
- Mishra, S., & Modi, S. B. (2013). Positive and Negative Corporate Social Responsibility, Financial Leverage, and Idiosyncratic Risk. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 117(2), 431–448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1526-9>
- Nguyen, P., & Nguyen, A. (2015). The effect of corporate social responsibility on firm risk. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 11(2), 324–339. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-08-2013-0093>
- Nirino, N., Battisti, E., Ferraris, A., Dell’Atti, S., & Briamonte, M. F. (2022). How and when corporate social performance reduces firm risk? The moderating role of corporate governance. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(6), 1995–2005. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2296>
- O’Neill, S. (2024, August 19). What is the difference between CSR and ESG? Corporate Governance Institute.
- Orlitzky, M., & Benjamin, J. D. (2001). Corporate Social Performance and Firm Risk: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Business & Society*, 40(4), 369–396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000765030104000402>
- Pan, F. (2021). *ESG disclosure and performance in Southeast Asia*. [sustainalytics.com](https://www.sustainalytics.com). <https://www.sustainalytics.com/esg-research/resource/investors-esg-blog/esg-disclosure-and-performance-in-southeast-asia>
- Park, S., Song, S., & Lee, S. (2017). Corporate social responsibility and systematic risk of restaurant firms: The moderating role of geographical diversification. *Tourism Management*, 59, 610–620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.09.016>
- PwC. (2021), “Beyond compliance: Consumers and employees want business to do more on ESG”. <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/services/consulting/library/consumer-intelligence-series/consumer-and-employee-esg-expectations.html>
- Salama, A., Anderson, K., & Toms, J. S. (2011). Does community and environmental responsibility affect firm risk? Evidence from UK panel data 1994–2006. *Business ethics: a European review*, 20(2), 192–204. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1457146>
- Sassen, R., Hinze, A. K., & Hardeck, I. (2016). Impact of ESG factors on firm risk in Europe. *Journal of Business Economics*, 86(8), 867–904. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11573-016-0819-3>

- Sciarelli, M., Landi, G., Turriziani, L., & Prisco, A. (2023). Does corporate sustainability mitigate firm risk? An empirical analysis on S&P 500 controversial companies. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 20(1), 38–58. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-09-2021-0388>
- Serikakhmetova, A. B., & Adambekova, A. A. (2022). Corporate Social Responsibility in the Context of ESG: Development and Current Trends. *Farabi Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.26577/fjss.2022.v8.i2.03>
- Shakil, M. H. (2021). Environmental, social and governance performance and financial risk: Moderating role of ESG controversies and board gender diversity. *Resources Policy*, 72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102144>
- Sustainable Stock Exchanges Initiative (SSE). (n.d.). *About*. <https://sseinitiative.org/about>
- Tian, L., (2022). Does ESG performance increase corporates' financial risk? Evidence from China. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4250033>
- Yoon, B., Lee, J. H., & Byun, R. (2018). Does ESG performance enhance firm value? Evidence from Korea. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10103635>
- Zhao, Y., Elahi, E., Khalid, Z., Sun, X., & Sun, F. (2023). Environmental, Social and Governance Performance: Analysis of CEO Power and Corporate Risk. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021471>.